

Linkage of student services: Reference letters, career advice and personal tutor systems

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Citation

Arp, Frithjof (2016). **Linkage of student services: Reference letters, career advice and personal tutor systems.** Accepted for and presented at the 2nd Teaching & Learning Conference, The University of Nottingham, Ningbo, China 2 September 2016. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.154138

Note

This extended abstract of the conference presentation is part of the public dissemination and consultation stage in the broader action research project:

Systems model of the action research process

Lewin, Kurt (1958: 201). *Group Decision and Social Change*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

Abstract

I report and reflect on a 24-months pilot project linking three service systems for students (Reference Letter-, Personal Tutor- and Career Advice-system) at the international branch campus (IBC) of a British university in China. The pilot project resulted from my role as faculty representative on the Student Career Development Committee (SCDC) and is part of a broader action research project. Data derive from the Student Barometer Survey, Summer Placement Program, focus groups, and discussions with faculty. Formalisation of policy and roll-out at university level of the linkage tested in the pilot project are proposed. Objectives include improving student learning outcomes, encouraging pro-active student behaviour, and enhancing the provision of services. The linkage of services may also help address the current imbalance of students gaining work experience after their undergraduate studies versus those pursuing immediate postgraduate studies overseas (currently less than 25% versus about 73%).

The interactive part of this presentation aims to gain further university-wide input from faculty members, in particular members of the Personal Tutor Network. Suggestions from SCDC meetings include that only students who can document participation in personal tutor meetings and practical work experience (at a minimum: summer placements / internships) should be given academic reference letters. On the other hand, undergraduate students that pursue practical work experience after graduation and before applying for postgraduate studies should receive formal assurance from the university that they will receive reference letters even after leaving the university (this is a major student concern). Outcomes of the interactive part will be considered in ongoing discussions with the Registrar, Vice-Provost Teaching & Learning, and the Management Board. Further updates on policy formalisation will be presented at additional events.

Student services are important for the international branch campuses (IBCs) of universities, but their specifics have largely escaped research attention. Their provision in the most efficient and effective way is crucial to institutions seeking to justify higher tuition fees than local competitors. Our action research on this topic complements the literature on the internationalisation of the higher education industry (Altbach & Knight, 2007; Bennett & Kane, 2011; Fielden, 2011). Specifically, we address issues of practical and theoretical importance to the management of IBCs (Shams & Huisman, 2011; Wilkins & Huisman, 2012).

References

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